

**THE TERM “BLENDING” AND ITS DEFINITION.
BLENDING IS A PRODUCTIVE WAY OF WORD FORMATION**

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Annotation: *this article is devoted to the study of blending as a new productive way of word formation and interpretation of the meaning of this term from the point of view of Russian and English linguists.*

Аннотация: *эта статья посвящена исследованию блендинга как нового продуктивного способа образования слова и интерпретации значения этого термина с точки зрения русских и английских лингвистов.*

Key words: *word-formation, blending, words – ingots, splinter.*

For many decades, the world's languages had greatly expanded their vocabulary. According to statistics, every year the dictionary of modern English increases by 15-20 thousand lexical units. The reasons for this addition to the vocabulary are obvious: the most pronounced and the most important reason is the social and cultural changes within modern society, technological revolution, and globalization. It is known that the English language is rapidly expanding its vocabulary, mainly resorting to word-forming and semantic resources, embedded in itself.

Initially, the method of blending was a rare way of forming new words and was mainly aimed at creating a stylistic effect in the conversation. Today, the number of words formed by merging has grown so much that they have become familiar and are no longer perceived as a witty and funny way to express their thoughts. Words that appear as a result of word-sharing are called blends.

Blended words have been popular because they allow us to shrink language, by merging two syllables which sound the same. Blending is as one of the types of word-formation considered to be not a new phenomenon since it was mentioned before, however due to globalization current blends are more creative that mostly found in mass media.

In the linguistic literature, the linguistic phenomenon of «blending» has a rather ambiguous definition. Linguists give different interpretations of blending. Moreover, there is no single term for this phenomenon.

In his work, A. P. Prokopec, while researching «blending», uses the term containment (contact, mixing) and defines it as «unification of the structural elements of two linguistic units in the speech stream on the basis of their structural similarity or identity, functional or semantic similarity». In turn, O. M. Lashkevich defines «blending» as a method of word formation, in which a new derivative word arises from the fusion of the full basis of one source word with the truncated basis of another or from the fusion of truncated bases of two original words. In the research of this author «blends» have the name - words - ingots. A. A. Khrushcheva believes that the blend is formed by the interaction of two or more initial units that undergo the truncation process and merge into a single token or have similar fragments in their structure and are combined by overlapping.

For example, A. Enarson presents «blending» as a combination of two or more forms in which at least one word was shortened. The abbreviation can be done by simply omitting a part of a word or can be the result of partially matching sounds or letters. S. Grice sees in «blending» creation of new tokens due to joining of parts of at least two other words, and at least one of them was reduced. In turn, A. Lerer says that blends are compounds that consist of one word and part of another, or parts of two other words. The truncated part of a word is called a splinter. Splinter cannot exist as a separate word.

It is interesting to note that the blended words most often appear in publicistic articles and consumer advertising texts (for which the principle is very important, «maximum meaning at minimum space», moreover, words-ingots attract special attention of the addressee). The spread of word expression is increasing in areas such as terminology in various fields of media, where a convenient, accurate and short method of communication is important.

Words created as a result of blending have a very important function: they allow a brief transmission of information and have an easy-to-use. Here is an example of the words that have been recorded in the language in the last decade, and the emergence of which is due to the emergence of new technologies, changes in society and other reasons: there was a popular English blend due to the withdrawal of United Kingdom from European Union called Brexit coming from Britain + Exit or substitution blends such as car +hijacking (carjacking), stool + stargazing (stoolgazing). The new form obtained in this way meets the two requirements of the language to the nomination: the integral design and compactness of the language.

Thus, blending as a method of word formation is becoming increasingly active and productive in many languages and requires further comprehensive study.

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